

SELECTION OF THE FEEDER WIRE CROSS-SECTION CONSIDERING VOLTAGE DROP LIMITATIONS

Chyzhevskiy V.

*Candidate of Technical Sciences,
National Technical University of Ukraine
"Igor Sikorsky Kyiv Polytechnic Institute",
Kyiv, Ukraine*

Abstract

The development of electrical networks is driven, amongst other things, by the need of the connections of the new consumers and sources of electrical energy to existing networks. This process is most active in low- and medium-voltage electrical networks, due, in particular, to the contracted capacity of consumers and the installed capacity of distributed energy sources.

During the design phase for connecting of the new power facilities to existing low- and medium-voltage electrical networks, an important task is selecting the cross-section of the wires or cables for the new feeders. In most cases, the selection of the wire or cable cross-section is based on the permissible current, followed by verification against the permissible voltage drop, which usually requires the calculation of steady-state operating parameters of the electrical network. This article discusses an approach to selecting the cross-section of feeder wires and cables in low- and medium-voltage networks, which makes it possible to avoid the need for such calculations and significantly simplifies the selection procedure.

Keywords: wire cross-section selection, low-voltage network, medium-voltage network, permissible voltage drop, permissible current.

Introduction

At present low-voltage (up to 1 kV) and medium-voltage (up to 35 kV) electrical networks are undergoing active expansion. This process is driven by the need of connection both new consumers and new sources of electrical energy, in particular distributed renewable

energy sources. Most power facilities of these types are connected to existing power networks using radial schemes. Such schemes involve connection of the new feeders either to branches of power lines or directly to substation busbars (Fig. 1).

Figure 1 – Wiring diagrams for consumers and energy sources in low- and medium-voltage electrical networks

The cross-section of wires and cables for new feeders is generally selected based on the permissible current rating, followed by a check by the permissible voltage drop [1]. This approach, at the stage of verifying the suitability of the selected cross-section in terms of permissible voltage drop, requires the calculation of the steady-state operating parameters of the electrical network to which the connection is being made. At the same time, during the feasibility study or preliminary calculations, information on the parameters of the existing electrical network may be incomplete or inaccurate,

which complicates the performance of the aforementioned verification. In such situation the approach to selecting the cross-section of the feeder wire or cable based on compliance with the requirements of regulatory documents regarding the permissible voltage drop on the feeder can be used. Using this approach significantly reduces the volume of calculations.

The principles of the proposed approach

It is known that the voltage drop across the power transmission line in the low- and medium-voltage electrical network shown in Fig. 2 can be determined as [2]:

Figure 2 – Feeder of electrical network

$$\underline{U}_1 = U_0 - \left[\left(\frac{P \cdot R + Q \cdot X}{U_0} \right) + j \left(\frac{P \cdot X - Q \cdot R}{U_0} \right) \right] = U_0 - (\Delta U' + j \Delta U''), \quad (1)$$

where:

U_0 – voltage at the beginning of the feeder (real number);

\underline{U}_1 – voltage at the end of the feeder;

$\Delta U'$, $\Delta U''$ – feeder active and reactive voltage drop components;

P , Q – consumer's active and reactive power;

R , X – feeder resistance and reactance.

It can be shown that for low- and medium-voltage electrical networks the effect of the reactive component of the voltage drop $\Delta U''$ on the magnitude of the voltage at the end of the feeder is very small. Therefore for such networks this voltage drop component can be neglected and (1) can be simplified:

$$U_1 = U_0 - \frac{P \cdot R + Q \cdot X}{U_0} = U_0 - \Delta U'. \quad (2)$$

Low-voltage case

For low-voltage electrical networks wire or cable reactance per unit length can be taken as 0,08 Ω/km [3], which is equal in values to the resistance per unit length of the aluminum 300 mm^2 in cross-section wire or cable or to the copper 240 mm^2 in cross-section wire or cable. Furthermore, in such networks, the consumed active power is usually 3 times or more greater than the consumed reactive power. Thus, for the low-voltage networks $P \cdot R \gg Q \cdot X$ so $Q \cdot X$ component in (2) can be neglected and (2) can be written as:

$$\Delta U' = \frac{P \cdot R}{U_0} = \frac{P \cdot \rho \cdot L}{U_0 \cdot S}, \quad (3)$$

where:

ρ – specific resistance of the wire material or cable conductor;

L – feeder length;

S – required wire or cable cross-section.

The maximum permissible voltage drop in feeders δU_{\max} for low-voltage electrical networks is regulated by the standard [1] and is known. So the required wire or cable cross-section S can be obtained as:

$$S = \frac{P \cdot \rho \cdot L}{U_0 \cdot \Delta U'}, \quad (4)$$

where $\Delta U' = \delta U_{\max}$.

Based on the calculated value, a larger standard wire or cable cross-section should be selected. The wire or cable cross-section determined in this way complies with the standards regarding permissible voltage drop, but must also be checked for permissible current I_{perm} :

$$I_{\text{perm}} \geq \frac{\sqrt{P^2 + Q^2}}{\sqrt{3} U_0}. \quad (5)$$

Medium-voltage case

For medium-voltage electrical networks wire or cable reactance per unit length often is equal or bigger than the resistance per unit length, so $Q \cdot X$ component

in (2) cannot be neglected. Equation (2) can be written in per unit length resistance r_0 and reactance x_0 as:

$$\Delta U' = \frac{P \cdot r_0 + Q \cdot x_0}{U_0} \cdot L. \quad (6)$$

In (6) r_0 and x_0 values are unknown and cannot be directly calculated from (6). Per unit length reactance can be written as:

$$x_0 = f \cdot \mu_0 \cdot \left(\ln \left(\frac{\sqrt{\pi} \cdot D_{GM}}{\sqrt{S}} \right) + \frac{\mu_r}{4} \right), \quad (7)$$

where:

f – electrical network nominal frequency;

D_{GM} – the geometric mean distance between phase wires or cables of the feeder;

μ_0 – vacuum magnetic permeability;

μ_r – the relative magnetic permeability of the wire material or cable conductor.

Taking (3) and (7) into account equation (6) can be rewritten as:

$$\Delta U' = \frac{P \cdot \frac{\rho}{S} + Q \cdot f \cdot \mu_0 \cdot \left(\ln \left(\frac{\sqrt{\pi} \cdot D_{GM}}{\sqrt{S}} \right) + \frac{\mu_r}{4} \right)}{U_0} \cdot L, \quad (8)$$

where $\Delta U' = \delta U_{\max}$ (for medium-voltage electrical network δU_{\max} value can be taken, for example, from standard [4]).

An analytical solution to equation (8) in general form requires the use of the complicated Lambert's W-function; it is therefore simpler to solve it for specific values of the variables. Based on the calculated value, a larger standard wire or cable cross-section should be selected. The wire or cable cross-section determined in this way complies with the standards regarding permissible voltage drop, but must also be checked for permissible current I_{perm} with (5).

Conclusions

An approach for determining the cross-sectional area of feeder wires or cables with reference of the requirements of standards regarding permissible voltage drop is proposed. An advantage of the proposed approach is that there is no need to calculate the steady-state operating parameters of the electrical network during the cross-sectional area determination stage. Furthermore, the main calculation expressions of the proposed approach are not tied to regional parameters or standards. This makes it possible to apply the proposed approach to determine the cross-sections of feeder wires or cables in electrical networks in any country in the world.

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